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Halimov A.A.,
Tulaboeva G.M.,
Sagatova H.M.,
Abdukadirova N.M.,
Muminov S.D.

Center for the development of professional
qualifications of medical workers,
department of cardiology and gerontology,
interventional cardiology and rhythmology course
y.Talipova@mail.ru

CHRONIC HEART FAILURE AND LIVER DYSFUNCTION (Literature review)

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ABSTRACT

Chronic heart failure is a chronic systemic disease, many scientific studies have shown that when it occurs, it affects some body organs, including the liver and kidneys. Liver dysfunction is common in patients with chronic heart failure, and these changes are directly related to hemodynamic parameters. The specificity of the vascular system of the liver and its high metabolic activity make its hemodynamic parameters weak and allow it to cause many molecular and hemodynamic changes. Currently, the systematization of the combined state of the heart and liver is being carried out, depending on the primary localization of the pathological process. The liver's cirrhosis includes several clinical, biochemical, histological and hemodynamic disorders. Chronic liver disease is caused by right ventricular and right ventricular heart failure. Alternatively, chronic liver cirrhosis is thought to be caused by elevated central venous pressure, pulmonary hypertension, constrictive pericarditis, mitral stenosis and tricuspid valve insufficiency.

Keywords: chronic heart failure, chronic liver disease, liver dysfunction, cirrhosis of the liver, right ventricular failure of the heart.

Халимов А.А.,
Тулабоева Г.М.,
Сагатова Х.М.,
Абдукадирова Н.М.,
Муминов С.Дж.

Центр повышения квалификации медицинских работников,
отделение кардиологии и геронтологии,
курс интервенционной кардиологии и ритмологии
y.Talipova@mail.ru

ХРОНИЧЕСКАЯ СЕРДЕЧНАЯ НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТЬ И ДИСФУНКЦИЯ ПЕЧЕНИ

(Литературный обзор)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Хроническая сердечная недостаточность является системным хроническим заболеванием, в ряде научных исследований доказано, что при ее возникновении поражает ряд органов тела, в том числе печень и почки. Специфика сосудистой системы печени и ее высокая метаболическая активность делают ее гемодинамические показатели слабыми и позволяют вызывать многие молекулярные и гемодинамические изменения. Дисфункция печени часто встречается у больных с хронической сердечной недостаточностью, и эти изменения напрямую связаны с гемодинамическими показателями. В настоящее время проводится систематизация сочетанного состояния сердца и печени в зависимости от первичной локализации патологического процесса. Цирроз печени включает ряд клинических, биохимических, гистологических и гемодинамических нарушений. Хроническая болезнь печени обусловлена правожелудочковой недостаточностью сердца. Альтернативно считается, что хронический цирроз печени вызывается повышением центрального венозного давления, легочной гипертензией, констриктивным перикардитом, а также митральным стенозом и недостаточностью трикуспидального клапана.

Ключевые слова: хроническая сердечная недостаточность, хроническая болезнь печени, дисфункция печени, цирроз печени, правожелудочковая недостаточность сердца.

Халимов А.А.,
Тулабоева Г.М.,
Сагатова Х.М.,
Абдукадилова Н.М.,
Муминов С.Дж.

Тиббиёт ходимларининг касбий малакасини ривожлантириш маркази,
кардтология ва геронтология, интервенцион кардиология
ва аритмология курси билан кафедраси
y.Talipova@mail.ru

**СУРУНКАЛИ ЮРАК ЕТИШМОВЧИЛИГИ ВА ЖИГАР ДИСФУНКЦИЯСИ
(адабиётлар шархи)****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Сурункали юрак етишмовчилиги тизимли сурункали касаллик бўлиб, бир қатор илмий тадқиқотлар шуни кўрсатдики, у пайдо бўлганда у бир қатор тана аъзоларига, шу жумладан жигар ва буйракларга таъсир қилади. Жигарнинг қон томир тизимининг ўзига хослиги ва унинг юқори метаболик фаоллиги унинг гемодинамик кўрсаткичларини заифлаштиради ва кўплаб молекуляр ва гемодинамик ўзгаришларни келтириб чиқаришга имкон беради. Сурункали юрак етишмовчилиги бўлган беморларда жигар дисфункцияси тез-тез учрайди ва бу ўзгаришлар гемодинамик параметрларга бевосита боғлиқ. Ҳозирги вақтда патологик жараённинг бирламчи локализациясига қараб, юрак ва жигарнинг комбинацияланган ҳолатини тизимлаштириш амалга оширилмоқда. Жигар сиррози бир қатор клиник, биокимёвий, гистологик ва гемодинамик бузилишларни ўз ичига олади. Сурункали жигар касаллиги ўнг қоринча ва ўнг қоринча юрак етишмовчилигидан келиб чиқади. Шу билан бир қаторда, сурункали жигар сиррози марказий веноз босимнинг кўтарилиши, ўпка гипертензияси, констриктив перикардит, митрал стеноз ва трикуспидал коптоқ етишмовчилиги туфайли юзага келади.

Калит сўзлар: сурункали юрак етишмовчилиги, сурункали жигар касаллиги, жигар дисфункцияси, жигар сиррози, юракнинг ўнг қоринча етишмовчилиги.

Introduction. Since chronic heart failure is a chronic systemic disease, it has been proven in many scientific studies that its occurrence affects many body organs, including the liver and kidneys

[1, 4, 12]. The specificity of the vascular system of the liver and its high metabolic activity makes its hemodynamic parameters weak and allow it to cause many molecular and hemodynamic changes.

Liver dysfunction is common in patients with chronic heart failure, and these changes are directly related to hemodynamic parameters [12].

Currently, the systematization of the combined state of the heart and liver depends on the primary localization of the pathological process. Liver cirrhosis includes several clinical, biochemical, histological and hemodynamic disorders. Chronic liver disease is caused by the heart's right ventricular and right ventricular heart failure. Alternatively, there is an understanding that chronic liver cirrhosis is caused by increased central venous pressure, pulmonary hypertension, constrictive pericarditis, mitral stenosis and tricuspid valve insufficiency [9, 10]. This epidemiological relationship was first fully and thoroughly described in 1951 by the famous hepatologist Sheloy Sherlock.

The main mechanism of liver edema is the filling of the central vein and liver hepatocytes with blood, and the development of local hypoxia, which leads to the appearance of dystrophic and atrophic changes in them. This condition, i.e., liver inflammation, leads to the development of fibrosis due to hepatocyte necrosis, collagen synthesis and blood circulation disorders. At the same time, the pressure in the portal vein does not exceed the pressure of the lower and upper caval veins, resulting in porto-caval anastomoses rarely developing [16].

Hepatic edema can be understood as increased venous blood pressure, leading to decreased perfusion and liver damage.

The term "Nutmeg liver" was proposed by Kiernan and Mallory, a scientist who identified and demonstrated the occurrence of central inflammation and focal necrosis of the liver as a result of blood circulation disorders in the liver [6].

The clinical appearance of liver cirrhosis is directly related to the stage of development and acceleration of heart failure. Suppose venous congestion develops rapidly in the liver in clinical practice. In that case, sharp pain under the right rib is associated with rapid expansion of the liver capsule, considered an acute abdominal symptom.

If chronic heart failure develops slowly, that is, over several months or years, then its clinical symptoms may prevail over the clinical symptoms of liver cirrhosis. Because this pathological condition is common, it is assumed that liver pathology has few or no symptoms.

One of the main complaints of patients in such cases is wheezing, shortness of breath, orthopnea in the objective examination, and cardiac complaints are also observed. In practice, the pain under the right rib and the discoloration of the skin are almost ignored, why? Because, in practice, the intensity of jaundice and pain symptoms in patients is low.

Objective indicators of the appearance of the liver, i.e., its enlargement, hardness, pain on palpation, and smoothness of the periphery, have great prognostic value in practice. It should be pointed out that the appearance of hepatjugular reflux is determined against the background of the expansion of the jugular veins in patients against the background of clinical symptoms of chronic heart failure [3].

A characteristic clinical feature of liver cirrhosis is that it changes depending on the state of central hemodynamics and the effectiveness of treatment of the main cause of heart failure, and the manifestation of its symptoms is manifested in different clinical manifestations.

Timely treatment of heart failure with a pathogenetic approach leads to a decrease in the size of the liver and a decrease in clinical signs of liver cirrhosis. Another characteristic feature of liver cirrhosis is the absence of signs of portal hypertension [16].

In the severe and decompensatory form of heart failure, the development of liver cirrhosis is accelerated. At the same time, cardiac liver cirrhosis gradually develops, and then ascites and splenomegaly occur. Patients' liver remains firm, with sharp edges and constant size, independent of treatment efficacy [4,5,7,8].

In most cases, liver transaminases, namely ALT, AST and bilirubin, do not exceed the normal values in a mild type of heart failure. But in its severe form, the activity of cytological markers and

the cholestatic syndrome is observed, and at the same time, the bilirubin indicator remains high [1,2,3].

In 30% of patients with cirrhosis, transaminase levels are 2-3 times higher than normal.

A significant decrease in the left ventricular ejection fraction is often observed with an increase in serum transaminase as a result of secondary ischemia in the liver. Observation of a cholestatic component in some patients can directly affect the increase of the gamma transferase and active phosphatase indicators, which can directly affect liver swelling and decrease perfusion [7,8,11,12].

An increase in glutamine transferase index is not only related to the severity of heart failure but also inextricably linked to a decrease in left ventricular ejection fraction and an increase in sodium uretic hormone index. Failure of the above indicators is also a reason for heart transplantation, and they, in turn, are considered predictors of death [13,15].

In clinical practice, it has been observed that hyperbilirubinemia is not typical for liver cirrhosis, but in severe heart failure, a significant increase in bound and unbound bilirubin is observed. This laboratory appearance, in turn, is predicted as a risk factor.

One of the complications of cirrhosis of the liver is cardiac cirrhosis, and during its development, dysproteinemia occurs. Ascites is characterized by an increase in the amount of protein in the ascites fluid and a significant increase in ascetic serum in the albumin gradient as a result of cirrhosis and liver cirrhosis [5,13].

In severe heart failure, increased uric acid levels, inflammation, metabolic changes, oxidative stress, endothelial dysfunction, and myocardial damage have been recognized as markers in many patients.

Patients with chronic heart failure may develop hyperuricemia due to decreased renal perfusion and urate excretion. there is a direct correlation between the pulmonary artery and the high pressure in the heart's right ventricle [4,5]. At the same time, it was observed that there is a direct correlation between the clinical signs of heart failure and increased pressure in the left ventricle of the heart [2].

To correctly diagnose liver cirrhosis, it is appropriate to diagnose viral hepatitis B and C, alcoholic liver disease, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, steatohepatitis, and drug-induced liver damage using immunoenzyme analysis or polymerase chain reaction [3,5,7].

We must remember that drugs used to treat cardiovascular diseases are metabolized in the liver, leading to side effects.

According to recommendations, echocardiography and ultrasound examinations are performed along with dopplerography of liver vessels in all patients with heart failure. When portal hypertension is not detected, in addition, in the tumor of the bile duct wall, a clear manifestation of liver inflammation is detected.

In severe clinical cases of heart failure, laparoscopy is used to confirm liver cirrhosis. During the examination, it can be seen that the liver has a dark red, brown, and yellow color like nutmeg [2,3,8].

In patients scheduled for a heart transplant, a routine liver biopsy is performed to detect liver cirrhosis due to ascites. Liver edema is characterized by venous edema in the sinusoid branch, blood congestion in the central lobes of the liver, expansion of the space of Disse, atrophy and necrosis.

The absence of pathological histological signs in the peripheral parts of the liver is a characteristic feature of liver inflammation, and venous inflammation does not reach these areas. Blood flow from the hepatic artery has been shown to protect hepatocytes from damage and eventually lead to hypertrophy [3,5].

Another important feature of liver transplantation is that venous congestion and fibrosis in the liver can be prevented when the standard of care recommended for the treatment of heart failure is followed. For the first time, Jolliffe and other scientists stated in the early 1930s that the basis of treatment for liver cirrhosis is that the effectiveness of etiologic pathogenetic treatment of cardiovascular and pulmonary heart failure diseases is observed by regression of clinical and biochemical results [7,8,12].

APF inhibitors, included in the standard treatment of heart failure, are metabolized in the liver, but when the liver is damaged and its dysfunction is observed, the drug's conversion to the active

substance slows down and becomes inactivated. This, in turn, is the basis for changing the daily amount of the drug. The views mentioned above also apply to drugs that reduce the activity of angiotensin-2 receptors, except for valsartan and irbesartan, as well as many selective and non-selective beta-adrenoblockers. In many cases, diuretics directly contribute to the reduction of venous congestion in the liver, thus reducing ascites and jaundice [4,7,9].

These drugs should be used with caution to prevent dehydration, hypotension, liver ischemia, and tertiary necrosis of liver lobes in patients with liver disease. When necessary, drugs, especially digoxin, should be prescribed with caution and in small doses because the toxic effect of the drug increases during liver function. The obtained data showed that anticoagulants are also used expediently, the probability of increased prothrombin time increases in patients, and even hypersensitivity to warfarin is noted [2,3,7].

Amiodarone, a drug with antiarrhythmic properties, is also intensively metabolized in the liver, but its dose reduction is not indicated in the instructions. Among the hypolipidemic drugs, statins can cause hypertransaminases by themselves, and the recommendation against statins is recognized only when ALT and AST increase by 3 times [9,10,13].

One of the treatment options is laparosynthesis, which is used in refractory cases. Still, it should be remembered that in patients with heart failure, protein loss and poor nutrition have been observed.

Therefore, in such patients, transjugular intrahepatic shunting or peritoneal shunting can be considered a contraindication, which aggravates the condition of its transition to a severe level in patients with heart failure [3]. In some cases, patients who do not respond positively to drug treatment are recommended for heart transplantation or installing an additional implant device of the left ventricle.

It is the hypoxic injury of the liver, which leads to liver perfusion and necrosis of hepatocytes in the central branch in sufficiently convincing indications [3,14]. The most common cases in practice are cardiogenic ischemic hepatitis or hepatic coma. The formation of liver coma occurs only in the combination of several pathological factors. Of these, significant hypoperfusion, slowness or violation of the activity of vascular collaterals, and the inability of the liver to increase oxygen consumption. A combination of these factors is manifested in acute myocardial infarction, cardiac arrhythmias, pulmonary vascular embolism, acute lung and heart failure, as well as massive blood loss, aortic aneurysm, depression, acute heart failure caused by septicemia, mainly in the right and left ventricles of the heart.

The incidence of hepatic coma observed in patients in clinical conditions ranges from 11 to 22%. It should be noted that cardiovascular pathology is the main cause of hepatic coma in 70% of cases. At the same time, acute respiratory failure, sepsis and liver coma may occur in 30% of patients [7].

According to the received information, liver dysfunction or hepatic coma is based on the following 3 criteria:

- acceleration of liver pathology against the background of cardiogenic shock or other acute clinical conditions,
- a significant increase in the level of transaminase in the blood serum that is, 20 times greater than the norm but quickly reversible;
- absence of other possible causes of liver damage.

The clinical appearance of liver coma also has its characteristics. Patients suffer from severe shortness of breath, pain under the right rib cage, and an increase in the size of the liver.

The obtained clinical observations proved that jaundice, oliguria, and clinical symptoms can be up to hepatic coma in rare cases. Characteristic changes in tests confirming liver dysfunction appear 12-24 hours after the event of acute cardiovascular failure. A sharp increase in ALT, AST and lactate dehydrogenase levels is observed. Clinical observations showed hyperbilirubinemia and coagulopathy in rare cases.

When the effects of etiological factors are eliminated, the listed indicators return to normal within five and ten days [5,7,9].

In the treatment guidelines, the main strategy for treating hepatic coma is to restore adequate liver perfusion through anti-shock measures, i.e., dopamine is recommended among drugs with a positive inotropic effect.

As a result of some scientific studies, the following metabolic drugs have been clinically useful in cases of liver encephalopathy: L-arginine, L-ornithine, L-aspartate and antibiotics. The outcome of a liver coma is directly determined by the state of the patient's cardiovascular system, as the death rate in this disease is determined by the underlying disease [3].

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ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

4 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

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